

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1970	Benito Navarrete Prieto	1990	1997			Spanish Full Professor of Art History	
1970	Professor Marion Gibson	1992	1997		w	British Professor of Renaissance and Magical Literatures	
1970	Ármann Jakobsson	1993	2003			Icelandic author and scholar (Early Icelandic Literature)	
1970	Ndubuisi Ahamefula	1993	No			Nigerian Lecturer in linguistics Igbo	
1970	Vitaly Chernetsky	1993	1996			Ukrainian-American Associate Professor and Director of Center for Russian, East European & Eurasian Studies	
1970	Lise Abrams	1993	1997		w	American cognitive psychologist	
1970	Nicolette Bethel	1993	2000		w	Bahamian teacher, writer and anthropologist	
1970	Amara Lakhous	1993				Algerian-Italian author, journalist and anthropologist	
1970	Steven Van Wolputte	1994	1998			Belgian professor of Social and cultural anthropology	
1970	Vicente Garcia Groyon	1994	No			Philippino Assistant Professor, Department of Literature (fiction)	
1970	Paweł Gancarczyk	1994	1999			Polish musicologist	
1970	John C. Hamer	1994				American-Canadian historian (religion) and mapmaker	
1970	Chiara Bertone	1995	2001		w	Italian Associate Professor of Sociology of Culture	
1970	Paweł Jędrzejko	1995	2000			Polish literary scholar and an Americanist, translation studies scholar, musician and yachtsman	
1970	Debora Diniz	1995	1999		w	Brazilian Anthropologist, bioethicist, human rights and health activist, university lecturer and documentary filmmaker	
1970	Karen Nakamura	1995	2001		w	American academic, author, filmmaker, photographer and the Robert and Colleen Haas Distinguished Chair of Disability Studies and Professor of Anthropology	
1970	Mark Rawlinson	1996	2002			British Associate Professor of History of Art (American art, photography, visual culture of 20th and 21st Centuries as well as critical and photographic theory)	
1970	Peter Buse	1996	1996			British professor and head of performance and screen studies	

1970 Christina Dokou	1996	1997	w	Greek Assistant Professor of American Literature and Culture
1970 Dr.Amal Riyadh Kitishat	1996	2006	w	Jordanian academian of College of Arts; Department: English Language
1970 Vincent Eltschinger	1996	2003		Swiss Professor Professor for Indian Buddhism (religious background, the apologetic dimensions and the intellectual genealogy of late Indian Buddhist philosophy)
1970 Robert M. Oppenheim	1996	2003		American scholar of Korean studies
1970 Metin Izeti	1997	2003		Albanian Professor of Art Philosophy, Aesthetics, Sociology of Art and Culture
1970 Elizabeth Otto	1997	2003	w	American Associate Professor of Art History and Visual Studies (issues of gender, history, and theory; and the history of photography, film, and media culture)
1970 Stefan Th. Gries	1997	2000		American Quantitative corpus linguist at the intersection of corpus linguistics, cognitive linguistics, and computational linguistics
1970 Antonis Balasopoulos	1997	1998		Greek Associate Professor of Comparative Literature
1970 Sverker Finnström	1997	2003		Swedish Associate Professor of Cultural Anthropology
1970 Omid Safi	1997	2000		American Professor of Asian and Middle Eastern Studies
1970 Jesper Juul	1998	2003		Danish Associate Professor at The Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts
1970 Tore Rye Andersen	1998	2007		Danish Associate Professor in Comparative Literature, researcher on Comparative Literature and Rhetoric
1970 Ute Verstegen	1998	1998	w	German professor for Christian Archaeology and Byzantine Art History
1970 Asier Barandiaran Amarika	1998	2003		Spanish (Basque) Professor Didactics of Language and Literature
1970 Елена Куликова	1998	2000	w	Russian literature critic
1970 Zsolt Almási	1999	2001		Hungarian Reader of English Renaissance Literature (Shakespeare, Tudor Culture, Digital Humanities)
1970 Juraj Šimko	1999	2010		Slovakian computer linguist

1970	Anneli Baran-Grzybek	1999	2011	w	Estonian folklorist and senior researcher of Estonian Literary Museum
1970	Erik Kwakkel	1999	2002		Dutch scholar who specializes in medieval manuscripts, paleography, and codicology
1970	Göran Larsson	1999	2000		Swedish professor in Religious Studies and deputy dean for the Faculty of Arts
1970	Scott Paeth	1999	2004		American Professor of Religious Studies
1970	Carlos Rojas	2000	2000		American cultural historian and his work and teachings primarily focus on Chinese culture
1970	Asier Barandiaran Amarika	2000	2002		Spanish Professor Didactics of Language and Literature
1970	Pasquale Orsini	2000			Italian palaeographer, librarian, and Professor from Università di Catania-Siracusa
1970	Kim Timby	2000	2006	w	American photography historian
1970	Hung Keung	2001	2014		Hong Kong new media artist (creative and research aspects of film, video and new media art internationally)
1970	Liina Lukas	2001	2006	w	Estonian Associate Professor of Comparative Literature, translator
1970	Lisbeth Klastrup	2001	2003	w	Danish scholar of new media
1970	Michael M Chemers	2001	2001		American Assoc Prof Dramatic Literature
1970	Katerina Harvati	2001	2001	w	Greek paleoanthropologist and expert in early human evolution
1970	J. Christopher Kovats-Bernat	2001	2001		American cultural anthropologist with a specialization in Haiti
1970	Tim Whitmarsh	2001	2006		British classicist and the second A. G. Leventis Professor of Greek Culture
1970	Elizabeth Shakman Hurd	2001	2002	w	American Professor of Politics and Religious Studies
1970	Charles Ofosu Marfo	2002	2005		Ghanian Head's Office Department of Modern Languages Faculty of Social Sciences
1970	Mohammad Isfironi	2002	2002		Indonesian Antropologist
1970	Nikhila H	2002	2002		Indian Associate Professor of Film Studies and Visual Communication
1970	Katrina Karkazis	2002	2002	w	American anthropologist and bioethicist, the Carol Zicklin Endowed Chair

1970	Kristen Ghodsee	2002	2002	w	Bulgarian-American ethnographer and Professor of Russian and East European Studies at the University of Pennsylvania	
1970	Brian Norman	2003	2004		American Dean, The Gwen Ifill College of Media, Arts, and Humanities (African American literature, with additional expertise in multi-ethnic and feminist traditions)	
1970	Esther Eidinow	2003	2003	w	British ancient historian and academic	
1970	Hans Ramduth	2005	2015		Moorish Senior Lecturer of School of Fine Arts (Art History and Art Theory)	
1970	Immanuel Schipper	2007	2017		German Senior Researcher and Research Project Manager at the Institute for Performing Arts and Film	
1970	Akmal Abdelrahman	2009	2009		Egyptian Associate professor art and design (Mural Design)	
1970	Candi K. Cann	2009	2009	w	American Associate Professor of Religion and BIC	
1970	Risper Namasaka Wepukhulu	2009	2009	w	Kenyan Senior Lecturer of Education Religious Studies	
1970	Alireza Jamshidnejad	2010	2010	w	Omani Assistant Professor of English language studies	
1970	Imad Hayif Sameer	2011	No		Iraqi Lecturer of Linguistics	
1970	Milena Bogdanova	2011	2015	w	Bulgarian researcher in Musicology and Music Arts	
1970	Benedetto Cipriani	2015	No		Italian Teacher and Ph.D. Student in Cultural Heritage and Territory	
1970	Manafova Gulnare Rafiq	2016	No	w	Azerbaijani Scientist in "Laboratory of national music research"	
1971	Jesse Hoffnung-Garskof	1991	2002		American Professor of History and American Culture	
1971	Francesca Dell'Acqua	1992	2001		Italian assistant professor in Medieval Art	
1971	Edwin Onwuka	1992	2008		Nigerian Lecturer in African and Comparative Literatures	
1971	Carl Edlund Anderson	1993	2000		Colombian Professor of Languages & Cultures	
1971	Elin Haugdal	1993	2008	w	Danish-Norwegian Professor in Art History, Department of Literature and Culture	
1971	Cyril Courtin	1993	1998	2010	French The first deaf researcher (signs)	1971-2010
1971	Eric Jarosinski	1993	2005		American Germanist, author, humorist, and public speaker	

1971	Matej Klemenčič	1994	2001		Slovenian Professor of Art History
1971	Ghil'ad Zuckermann	1995	2003		Israeli-born revivalist and linguist
1971	Gregory Buchakjian	1995	2017		Lebanese photographer, filmmaker and art historian
1971	Marc Miyake	1995	1999		American (Hawaii) linguist (historical linguistics, Old Japanese and Tangut)
1971	Jaco Beyers	1995	2002		South African Associate Professor in the Department of Science of Religion and Missiology
1971	Ben Zimmer	1996	1999		American linguist, lexicographer, and language commentator
1971	Sylvie Octobre	1996	1996	w	French sociologist (cultural practices of children and adolescents)
1971	Beata Megyesi	1996	2002	w	Swedish Associate Professor in computational linguistics, Department of Linguistics and Philology
1971	Risto Järv	1996	2005		Estonian folklorist (folklore, fairy tale, narrative)
1971	Rane Willerslev	1996	2003		Danish anthropologist
1971	Candy Gunther Brown	1996	2000	w	American Professor of Religious Studies
1971	Jenny Davidson	1997	1999	w	American historian and writer who writes about 18th-century literature, etiquette and culture
1971	Pavína Šaldová	1997	2005	w	Czech philologist, specialization in English linguistics, publications
1971	Gerd Bayer	1997	2004		German Professor of English Literature and Cultural Studies
1971	Sujay Kumar Mandal	1997	2007		Indian Associate Professor of Folklore
1971	Grażyna Darlak	1997	1997	w	Polish musicologist
1971	Shintarō Arakawa	1997	2002		Japanese linguist who specializes in the study of the extinct Tangut language
1971	Lars Krutak	1998	1998		American anthropologist, photographer, and writer (tattoo and its cultural background)
1971	Patrick Goethals	1998	2000		Belgian linguist
1971	Marika Butskhrikidze	1998	2001	w	Georgian linguist
1971	Nino Amiridze	1998	2002	w	Georgian linguist
1971	Solehah Yaacob	1998	2005	w	Malaysian professor of Philosophy of Arabic Grammar
1971	Maria Elena Buszek	1999	2003	w	American scholar, critic, curator, and associate professor of art history

1971	Alexander Streitberger	1999	2004		German Professor of Modern and Contemporary Art History
1971	Evina Sistakou	1999	1999	w	Greek Professor of Greek Literature
1971	Adi Yasran Bin Abdul Aziz	1999	2005		Malaysian Professor of Malay Language
1971	Mihaela Ursa	1999	2004	w	Romanian Assoc. Prof. of Comparative Literature
1971	Selena Rakocevic	1999	2009	w	Serbian cultural and literary connections between India and Slovenia
1971	Oksana Samusenko	1999	2004	w	Ukrainian philologist (Russian and Ukrainian as foreign Languages, Linguistic and Cultural Studies, ethnolinguistics)
1971	Eva Liina Asu-Garcia	1999	2004	w	Estonian Associate Professor of Swedish Language, phonetician
1971	Dr.Afshin Amoozadeh Ichaei	1999	2010		Iranian Assistant Prof. Fine and Theatre Arts
1971	Karen Redrobe	1999	1999	w	American the Elliot and Roslyn Jaffe Endowed Professor in Film Studies and chair of the department of the History of Art at the University of Pennsylvania
1971	Katajun Amirpur	1999	2000	w	German professor of Islamic Studies
1971	Ibtihal Mahdi Abdulkareem Al-Tameemi	2000	2005	w	Iraqi assistant Professor in General Linguistics and Translation
1971	Isabelle Bernard	2000	2000	w	French Professor of French Literature
1971	Laurence Boulègue	2000	2000	w	French Professor of Universities in Latin and Neolatin Language and Literature (UPJV)
1971	María Magdalena Ziegler Delgado	2000	2015	w	Venezueli Professor of History of Art and Culture
1971	Palle Dahlstedt	2000	2004		Swedish composer, Associate professor, Information technology and music
1971	Pelle Snickars	2000	2001		Swedish professor of media and communication sciences (digital humanities)
1971	Saghar Sharifi	2000	2012	w	Iranian Assistant Professor of Linguistics
1971	Vehbi Miftari	2000	2009		Albanian Profesor of Albanian Literature
1971	Luz Maria Sanchez Cardona	2000	2007	w	Mexican Chair of the Department of Arts and Humanities
1971	Matthew Wynn Sivils	2001	2006		American professor of English (formerly a wildlife biologist)

1971	Mezzetti Monia	2001	2006	w	Italian assistante professor of French Literature
1971	Nanashaitu Aduke Umoru-Oke	2001	2016	w	Nigerian Senior lecturer of history art (Visual Arts, Ceramics (Art History), and Pottery (Archaeology))
1971	Shaka McGlotten	2001	2005		American Professor of Media Studies
1971	Srdjan Vuletic	2001	No		Bosnian filmmaker
1971	Olakunbi Olasope	2001	2005	w	Nigerian expert on Roman social history, Greek and Roman theatre, and Yoruba classical performance culture
1971	José Ignacio Pichardo Galán	2002	2008		Spanish professor of cultural and social Anthropology
1971	Patrick Levačić	2002	2011		Croatian Assistant Professor of French literature
1971	R Lalitha Raja	2002	2004	w	Indian Assistant Professor in Linguistics
1971	Johnson Akpakpan	2002	2011		Nigerian Senior Lecturer, Music Departemnt
1971	Emiliana Cruz	2002	2011	w	Mexican contemporary linguistic anthropologist
1971	Robby Waddell	2003	2003		American Pentecostal biblical scholar, pastor, and activist
1971	Guido Seiler	2003	2003		German linguist (German and Slavic Studies)
1971	Karen Ho	2003	2003	w	American anthropologist, contributed to anthropological research in Wall Street culture
1971	Anna Nacher	2004	2006	w	Polish Associate Professor at the Institute for Audiovisual Arts (posthumanism, media theory, digital visuality, media art, sound art, sound studies, e-literature and art games)
1971	Ekrema Shehab	2004	2007		Palestinean researcher of Department of English Language and Literature
1971	Helena Dobrovljc	2004	2004	w	Slovenian linguist
1971	Mohammad Shaaban Deyab	2004	2004		Egyptian professor of English Literature (American & British Literature, Rhetoric)
1971	Ulrich Götz	2004	2004		Swiss Professor, Head of Subject Area in Game Design
1971	Timothy M. Stirtz	2004	2004		American linguist (grammar)
1971	Marijana Nikolić	2004		w	Bosnian Associate Professor at the Department of Bosnian Language and Literature

1971	Mohammad Almostafa	2005	2012		Jordanian Associate Professor of English Literature (Postcolonialism, Feminism, Arab American Literature, English and Arabic Poetry)
1971	Rotimi Olanrele Oladipupo	2005	2014		Nigerian Doctor of English Phonology
1971	Parisa Gorbannejad	2005	2005	w	Iranian Associate Professor in History of Culture and Civilization of Islamic Nation
1971	Ivelina Stoyanova	2006	No	w	Bulgarian Research assistant, Department of Computational Linguistics
1971	Dijana Nazor	2006	2016	w	Croatian culture scientist
1971	Ahmed Hayder Sigar	2007	2007		Iraqi Head of the Department of Translation, Faculty of Humanities (linguist), former employee of Ministry of Education
1971	Nahid Mohammadi	2007	2008	w	Iranian assistant professor of English Literature (Ecocriticism, Literary Theories, Poetry, American Literature, Interdisciplinary Studies, Gender Studies, Comparative Literature)
1971	Zeinab Nour	2007	2007	w	Egyptian Associate Professor, Painting Department
1971	Marios Koukounaras-Liagkis	2007	2008		Greek Assistant Professor, Faculty of Theology
1971	Catalin Stefanescu Patrascu	2008	2008		Romanian professor of guitar
1971	Onya McCausland	2008	2017	w	British painter, Senior Research Fellow, Slade School of Fine Art
1971	Mohammad Manzoor Malik	2008	2008		Indian Lecturer of Philosophy and Religion
1971	Ezzeldin Mahmoud Tajeldin Ali	2009	2011		Saudi Arabian associate professor of phonetics and experimental linguistics
1971	Saiantiago Villafan	2009			Philipino bilingual poet who writes in English and in his native language of Pangasinan
1971	Brandi Denison	2010	2011	w	American Associate Professor of Religious Studies
1971	Edith Naliaka Simiyu	2012		w	Kenyan Tutorial Fellow of Religion
1971	Vesela Kazashka	2013	2014	w	Bulgarian Assistant Professor of Academy of Music, Dance and Fine Arts
1972	Rebecca Grinter	1993	1996	w	British professor in the School of Interactive Computing

1972 Scott Bradley Cook	1995	1995		American Professor of Chinese History, Literature, and Philosophy
1972 Padraic Monaghan	1995	2000		British professor of English Linguistics
1972 Ozioma Onuzulike	1995	2007		Nigerian ceramics artist, poet and art historian, Professor of Ceramic Art and African Art and Design History
1972 Paul Baker	1995	2002		British linguist (corpus linguistics, critical discourse analysis, corpus-assisted discourse studies and language and identity, language of Polari)
1972 Kecia Ali	1995	2002	w	American scholar of Islam who focuses on the study of Islamic Jurisprudence (fiqh) and Women in Early and Modern Islam
1972 Golan Levin	1996	No		American new media artist, composer, performer and engineer
1972 Katherine Kuenzli	1996	2002	w	American Professor of Art History (European modernism, 1880-1940)
1972 Pavel Kosek	1996	2006		Czech associate professor, Department of Czech Language
1972 Mads Rosendahl Thomsen	1996	2002		Danish Professor in Comparative Literature
1972 Reza Yavarian	1996	2007		Iranian Assistant professor of English language and literature (literature, cultural studies, film studies)
1972 Mari Sarv	1996	2008	w	Estonian Senior researcher (folklore, archives, poetics, digital humanities, cultural studies)
1972 Sofia Dahl	1996	2006	w	Swedish Associate Professor in Music perception and Cognition
1972 Arienne Dwyer	1996	1996	w	American professor of Linguistic Anthropology
1972 Frederico Fernandes	1997	2003		Brazilian Professor of Theory of Literature
1972 Anshuman Mondal	1997	2000		British Professor of Modern Literature, (post-colonial studies)
1972 Vanessa Guignery	1997	2000	w	French Professor of English Literature and Postcolonial Literature
1972 Kleanthes K. Grohmann	1997	2000		German Professor of Biolinguistics
1972 Eric Hayot	1997	2009		Swedish Distinguished Professor of Comparative Literature and Asian Studies

1972	Simon Horobin	1997	2002		British philologist and bestselling author
1972	Catherine Padmore	1998	2002	w	Australian fiction writing lecturer (literary studies and creative writing)
1972	Anouk de Koning	1998	2005	w	Dutch Associate Professor of Cultural Anthropology and Development Sociology
1972	Kristi Viiding	1998	2002	w	Estonian Senior Researcher Estonian Academy of Sciences Under and Tuglas Literature Centre
1972	Alexandre François	1998	2001		French linguist (description and study of the indigenous languages of Melanesia)
1972	Louise Leakey	1998	2001	w	Kenyan paleontologist and anthropologist
1972	Anita Hrnjak	1998	2015	w	Croatian professor of russian language
1972	Farshid Delshad	1998	2000		Iranian Lecturer of Persian and Comparative Linguistics
1972	Joel Wendland-Liu	1998	2002		American Associate Professor of Integrative, Religious, and Intercultural Studies
1972	Søren Frank	1999	2006		Danish Professor of Comparative Literature
1972	Bettina van Hoven	1999	1999	w	German-Dutch Associate Professor in the field of Cultural Geography
1972	Maurizio Fiorilla	1999	2003		Italian associate professor of Philology of Italian Literature
1972	Julie Anne Legate	1999	2002	w	American linguist who works in the areas of syntax and morphology
1972	Elizabeth (Dori) Tunstall	1999	1999	w	American Black design anthropologist, researcher, academic leader, writer, and educator
1972	Miriyam Aouragh	1999	2008	w	Dutch anthropologist who specializes in social media and internet activism
1972	Shang-Wen Wang	1999	2011		Thai Assistant Professor, Department of Philosophy & Religion
1972	Ellen Swift	1999	1999	w	British archaeologist and Professor of Roman Archaeology at the University of Kent
1972	Gisli Magnusson	2000	2005		Danish Professor of Danish Literature
1972	Petr Šámal	2000	2006		Czech researcher, Department for Research into Literary Culture, Faculty Member
1972	Sachin C. Ketkar	2000	2002		Indian Professor of English, Department of English, Faculty of Arts

1972	Sigrid Røyseng	2000	2007	w	Norwegian professor and cultural sociologist
1972	Чорна Лариса Сергіївна	2000	2001	w	Ukrainian philosopher (історія української філософської думки, філософія освіти)
1972	Delia Grigore	2000	2002	w	Romanian (Romani) writer, philologist, academic and Romani rights activist
1972	Ashk Dahlén	2000	2002		Swedish-Iranian scholar, linguist, Iranologist, and translator of classical Persian literature
1972	Yendo Afgani	2000	2013		Malaysian senior lecturer, Antropology Dakwah
1972	Mikel Burley	2000			British Associate Professor of Religion and Philosophy
1972	Arbaayah Ali Termizi	2001	2005	w	Malaysian associate professor at the Department of English, Faculty of Modern Languages and Communication
1972	Ljerka Dulibic	2001	2007	w	Serbian Senior Research Associate and Curator of Italian paintings at the Strossmayer Gallery of Old Masters
1972	Rodrigo Gutiérrez-Bravo	2001	2002		Mexican linguist
1972	Miodarka Tepavčević	2001	2007	w	Montenegrin linguist (Syntax, Morphology, Lexicology)
1972	Birk Weiberg	2002	2014		German art historian (history and theory of photographic images, contemporary and media arts)
1972	Mobolanle Sotunsa	2002	2005	w	Nigerian Professor of African Oral Literature and Gender Studies
1972	Saverio Tomaiuolo	2002	2010		Italian Lecturer, English Literature and Language
1972	Judith Bishop	2002	2002	w	Australian poet, linguist and translator
1972	Jaleh Mansoor	2002	2007	w	American art historian, critic, and theorist of modern and contemporary art
1972	Henrik Bogdan	2002			Swedish Professor of Religious Studies
1972	David T. Ngong	2002	2007		Cameroonian-American Associate Professor of Religion and Theology
1972	Dan Hicks	2003	2003		British archaeologist and anthropologist
1972	Ahmad Muttaqin	2003	2012		Indonesian Lecturer at the Department of Religious Studies
1972	Prof. Sanjay Kumar Jha	2004	2004		Indian Director of Liberal Arts and Foreign Languages at the Amity University
1972	Мугтасимова Гульназ Ринатовна	2004	2005	w	Russian philologist (lingvofolkloristika, lexicology, Translation)

1972	America Meredith	2004	No	w	Swedish-Cherokee painter, curator, educator, and editor
1972	Clea Koff	2004	No	w	American forensic anthropologist
1972	Zanny Begg	2005	2011	w	Australian Lecturer at UNSW Art & Design, filmmaker
1972	Юша Жанна Монгеевна	2005	2006	w	Russian folklorist
1972	Reza Aslan	2005	2009		Iranian-American scholar of religious studies, writer, and television host
1972	Eneken Laanes	2006	2009	w	Estonian Associate Professor of Comparative Literature and Culture Analysis
1972	Omar Colombo	2006	2009		Italian lecturer Applied Linguistics (Italian and French as a Foreign Languages)
1972	Andrea Berez-Kroeker	2006	2011	w	American documentary linguist (Athabaskan and Chimbu-Wahgi languages)
1972	Siniša Runjaić	2007	2007		Croatian Senior Associate at the Department of General Linguistics
1972	Phan Thi Thanh Thao	2007		w	Vietnamese Lecturer of University of Foreign Languages
1972	Olugbemi Berekiah	2007	2017		Nigerian Senior Lecturer, Department of Religious Studies
1972	Tom Uytterhoeven	2008	No		Belgian Candidate PhD of Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies
1972	Ayo Oluranti	2009	2012		Nigerian Music Senior Lecturer
1972	Sandra Vitaljic	2010	2010	w	Bosnian Professor of Photography, Academy of Dramatic Arts, painter
1972	Nataša Stanišić	2010	No	w	Serbian Lecturer in English Language and Literature
1972	Tanvir Badruddin Syed	2011	2017	w	Indian Assistant Professor of Milliya Art's, Science and Management Science college (woman studies)
1972	Manuela Naveau	2012	2015	w	Austrian artist, Curator of Ars Electronica Linz, Guest professor University for Art and Industrial Design
1972	Edgar Nabutanyi	2012	2012		Ugandan Lecturer of Literature
1972	Cătălina Constantinovici	2013	2013	w	Romanian Music teacher
1973	Charles Yang	1993	2000		American Professor in the Department of Linguistics, Computer Science, and Psychology
1973	Garnet Hertz	1995	2009		Canadian artist, designer and academic
1973	Sophie Berrebi	1995	2002	w	French writer, art historian and exhibition curator

1973	Emily M. Bender	1996	2000	w	American linguist (multilingual grammar engineering)
1973	Antonio Urquizar-Herrera	1996	2000		Spanish Full Professor of History of Art
1973	Johannes Angermüller	1996	2003		German discourse researcher in linguistics and sociology
1973	Richard McElreath	1997	2001		American professor of anthropology
1973	Elizabeth Stephens	1997	2012	w	Australian Associate Professor in Cultural Studies
1973	Agnès Bos	1997	2000	w	British Lecturer in Art History
1973	Anikó Lipták	1997	2001	w	Dutch linguist
1973	Liina Lindström	1997	2005	w	Estonian linguist
1973	Liudmyla Slavova	1997	2000	w	Ukrainian linguist
1973	Constanza Ceruti	1997	2001	w	Argentinean pioneer in the anthropological study of sacred mountains around the world, and in the emerging field of glacial archaeology
1973	David J. Getsy	1998	2002		American art historian, curator, and art writer
1973	Angela A Frattarola	1998	2004	w	American Director, Language and Communication Centre
1973	Roman Kuhar	1998	2009		Slovenian professor of sociology (gender, sexuality, LGBT, popular culture and everyday life)
1973	Svitlana Hrytsenko	1998	1999	w	Ukrainian philologist
1973	Liina Paales	1998	2011	w	Estonian freelance folklorist (Deaf culture, Deaf folklore, Deaf history)
1973	Roberta D'Alessandro	1998	2004	w	Italian Professor of Syntax and Language Variation
1973	Janet Bellotto	1999	No	w	Canadian painter, writer and sculptor
1973	Ivana Lazarević	1999	2012	w	Croatian art historian and Demographic Historian
1973	Sven-Erik Soosaar	1999	2017		Estonian Senior Lexicographer
1973	Ekaterina Velmezova	1999	2000		Swiss Russian-born philologist, professor of Slavistics and of history and epistemology of language sciences in Eastern Europe, history and epistemology of language sciences in Central and Eastern Europe
1973	Mark Turin	1999	2006		British anthropologist, linguist and radio broadcaster who specializes in the Himalayas and the Pacific Northwest
1973	Sabine Chaouche	1999	1999	w	French Professor of Theatre and Cultural History
1973	László Fejes	2000	2000		Hungary researcher in Historical Linguistics, Computational Linguistics and Morphophonology

1973	Philomen Probert	2000	2000	w	British classicist and academic, specialising in linguistics
1973	Penelope Petsini	2000	2003	w	Romanian lecturer of photography theory and contemporary art
1973	Gabriele Marranci	2000	2003		Italian anthropologist working on religion with a specialization in Muslim societies
1973	Alma Denić-Grabić	2000		w	Bosnian Associate Professor at the Department of Bosnian Language and Literature
1973	Oliver Krüger	2000	2004		German professor in Religious studies
1973	Anthi Papageorgiou	2001	2001	w	Greek Professor of Theory and Practice of Translation of Department of Italian and Spanish Language and Literature
1973	Gabriela Aceves Sepulveda	2001	2014	w	Mexican Canadian cultural historian and interdisciplinary media artist (intersections of video and performance with a research focus on feminist media, visual culture and Latin American art history)
1973	Maris Saagpakk	2001	2007	w	Estonian Associated Professor at the Institute of Germanic and Romance Languages and Cultures
1973	Zoila Elena Vega Salvatierra	2001	2015	w	Peruan Profesora de investigación musical
1973	Dikdik Sayahdikumullah	2001	2012		Indonesian painter, Lecturer of Visual Art
1973	Gerd Jendraschek	2001	2004		German linguist (Basque, Turkish, and latmul)
1973	Gabriella Coleman	2001	2005	w	Puerto Rican anthropologist, academic and author whose work focuses on hacker culture and online activism, particularly Anonymous
1973	Annette Yoshiko Reed	2001	2002	w	American Associate Professor of Religious Studies
1973	Matthew Fraleigh	2002	2005		American Associate Professor of East Asian Literature and Culture and chair of the Program in Comparative Literature
1973	Patraş Antonio	2002	2002		Romanian Professor of Literature
1973	Sindre Bangstad	2002	2007		Norwegian social anthropologist
1973	Joan Duran-Porta	2003	2003		Spanish Professor of Medieval Art
1973	Julia Bryan-Wilson	2003	2004	w	American Professor in the Department of History of Art
1973	Antonia Syson	2003	2003	2018 w	British-American classical scholar specialising in the study of Virgil's Aeneid

1973-2018

1973	Katja Rados-Perkovic	2004	2011	w	Croatian Assistant Professor of Italian Literature (Italian 18th century theatre, Italian librettos, Croatian translations of Italian literature)
1973	Martin Simonson	2004	2006		Swedish scholar, novelist, and translator, specialized in fantasy literature and nature writing
1973	Noel B. Salazar	2004	2008		French sociocultural anthropologist
1973	Greg Dvorak	2004	2008		American Associate Professor of Pacific and Asian History and Cultural Studies
1973	Katarina Wadstein MacLeod	2005	2006	w	Swedish Professor Art History (femininity and domesticity; bodies and gender; cultural heritage and value; narration of centre and periphery)
1973	Scott Andrew Crossley	2005	2006		American linguist
1973	Hossein Aliakbari Harehdasht	2006	2012		Iranian assistant professor of English Language and Literature
1973	Osakue Omoera	2006	2016		Nigerian Associate Professor in the Department of English and Communication Studies
1973	Ruth-Helene Melioranski	2006	No	w	Estonian design researcher, Estonian Academy of Arts
1973	Sanel Hadžiahmetović Jurida	2006	2012		Bosnian professor at the Faculty of English Language and Literature
1973	Youngsun Yoon	2006	2009	w	Korean Associate Professor, Korean & Comparative Literature, and Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies Program
1973	Edilson Silva Liévano	2007	2013		Colombian Professor literature, communication and culture, reading, writing and fiction (novel)
1973	Jayson Beaster-Jones	2007	2007		American Associate Professor of Music in the Global Arts Studies Program
1973	Riham Tahoun	2007	2007	w	Egyptian lecturer in german language
1973	Alice Roberts	2007	2008	w	British English biological anthropologist, biologist, television presenter and author
1973	Seyed Mohammad Hosseini-Maasoum	2009	2009		Iranian Associate Professor. Faculty of Human Sciences (Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies)
1973	Odoh George	2011	2014		Nigerian Lecturer in Painting and Drawing (painter)

1973 Bakhtiar Hama	2012	2014		Iraqi Professor of Literature in English (Literature in English, Modern British and American Drama, Stylistics)
1973 Eleni Kamma	2012			Greek artist, PhD Arts candidate
1973 Beruniy Alimov	2013			Uzbeki Senior Lecturer, Faculty of International Journalism
1973 Tom Keefe	2017	No		American Chair of Liberal Arts at Rocky Mountain College of Art + Design
1973 Vesna Waite	2019	2019	w	Serbian English Language Teacher
1974 Nathan E. Richardson (Nathan Richardson)	1994	1998		American Professor of Spanish, Department Chair, Modern Languages and Literatures
1974 Hilaire Kallendorf	1994	2000	w	American Professor of Hispanic and Religious Studies and a Cornerstone Faculty Fellow in Liberal Arts
1974 Asifa Majid	1995	2001	w	British Professor of language, communication, and cultural cognition
1974 Reet Hiimäe	1995	2017	w	Estonian senior researcher in the folk tales and religion working group (Estonian Literary Museum)
1974 Miriam Taverniers	1996	2002	w	Belgian linguist
1974 Roman Soloviy	1996	2000		Ukrainian Senior Researcher, Center for the Study of Religion
1974 Koenraad Brosens	1997	2002		Belgian Full Professor & Chair, Art History
1974 Boban Arsenijevic	1997	2006		Serbian linguist
1974 Natalie M. Underberg-Goode	1997	2002	w	American Associate Professor of Digital Media and Folklore
1974 Ákos Bertalan Apatóczy	1997	2006		Hungarian Sinologist and Mongolist, mostly known for his historical linguistic research on Middle Mongol sources written in Chinese script
1974 Irfan Ahmad	1997	2005		Indian anthropologist and senior research fellow at the Max Planck Institute for the Study of Religious and Ethnic Studies
1974 Joshua Hagen	1998	2003		American Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences
1974 Paraic Finnerty	1998	2001		American Reader in English & American Literature
1974 Juanito Ornelas de Avelar	1998	2006		Brazilian linguist

1974	Angela Aujla	1998	2002	w	Indian the Experienced Professor Of Sociology and Cultural Studies
1974	Cutaru Caius	1998	2011		Romanian Assistant Professor of History of Religions
1974	Hanne Martine Eckhoff	1999	2007	w	Norwegian linguist
1974	Violeta Popa Preda	1999	No	w	Romanian Assistant professor of Literature
1974	Mahrus eL-Mawa	1999	2009		Indonesian teacher of islamic studies, especially philology
1974	Liina Saarlo	1999	2006	w	Estonian researcher (folklorist), Estonian Literary Museum
1974	Catherine Spooner	2000	2000	w	British Professor of Literature and Culture (Gothic literature, film and popular culture, fashion and costume)
1974	Martin A. Hainz	2000	2000		Austrian philologist, theorist and philosopher
1974	Titus Hjelm	2000			Finnish Associate Professor in the Study of Religion
1974	Daniel Cohnitz	2000	2005		Dutch chair for theoretical philosophy
1974	Carmen Vioreanu	2001	2011	w	Romanian Associate Professor of Faculty of Foreign Languages and Literatures (Scandinavian Studies, Icelandic Sagas, Theater, History of Scandinavia)
1974	Marcello Potocco	2001	2006		Slovenian literary comparator, literary theorist, poet and translator
1974	Nicolas Nova	2001	2007		French Associate Professor at the Geneva School of Art and Design
1974	Xiaoye You	2001	2005		Chinese Liberal Arts Professor of English and Asian Studies
1974	Mehrdad Aghaei Hashjin	2001	2008		Iranian Assistant Professor of Arabic Language and Literature
1974	Liv Ingeborg Lied	2001	2007	w	Norwegian theologian
1974	Mohammed AlJedy	2001	2014		Palestinean Assistant Professor of Usul al-Din and Comparative Religion
1974	Ahlam Sbaihat	2002	2002	w	Jordanian (Irbid) Professor of Spanish Language and Literature
1974	Danny Butt	2002	2012		Australian Associate Director (Research) at Victorian College of the Arts
1974	Gerardo de Simone	2002	2006		Italian Professor of History of Art
1974	Luca Cignetti	2002	2009		Italian Professor of Didactics of Italian languages

1974	Сафина Римма Абельхаеровна	2002	2003	w	Russian philologist (сопоставительная лингвистика, фразеология, политическая лингвистика)	
1974	Anastasia Gubaydullina	2002	2003	w	Russian literature critic (creative writing, literature cross-writing, literature for children, critical thinking)	
1974	Arleen Ionescu	2002	2002	w	Romanian Professor of English Literature and Critical Theory	
1974	Jordina Gort Oliver	2002		w	Spanish Professor of Language and Literature	
1974	Blaž Šeme	2003	2005		Slovenian Assistant Professor and Researcher in fine art	
1974	Maria Grazia Sindoni	2003	2003	w	Italian Associate Professor English language and translation	
1974	Tatiana Dubrovskaya	2003	2003	w	Russian Head of the English Language Department	
1974	Mevlida Đuvić	2003		w	Bosnian Associate Professor at the Department of Bosnian Language and Literature	
1974	Anja Mrak	2004	2004	w	Slovenian literature critic (feminism, gender studies)	
1974	Josef Benson	2004	2012		American associate professor of Literatures and Languages	
1974	Tatjana Adamović	2004	2015	w	Serbian reseraher at Institute for Experimental Phonetics and Speech Pathology	
1974	Andronika Martonova	2004	2006	w	Bulgarian culture scientist (cinema)	
1974	John J. McGraw	2004		2016	American assistant professor in the Departments of Religious Studies and Central American Studies	1974-2016
1974	Jaime Baquero de la Calle Rivadeneira	2004			Ecuadorian Professor of "Philosophy of Law", "Social Doctrines" and "Law and Religion"	
1974	Peter Manseau	2004	2009		American the Lilly Endowment Curator of American Religious History	
1974	Alex Nelungo Wanjala	2005	2009		Kenyan Senior Lecturer, Department of Literature & Sub-Department of French (Postcolonial Studies, Cultural Studies, Feminism, Gender Studies, Kenyan Literature, East Africa)	
1974	Anita Triastuti	2005	No	w	Indonesian Lecturer of English Language Education	
1974	Radek Čech	2005	2005		Czech quantitative linguist	
1974	Uri Mor	2005	2009		Israeli Senior Lecturer (tenured), Department of Hebrew Language	

1974	Каранда Марина Василівна	2005	2006	w	Ukrainian culturologist (християнська естетика та мистецтво, неорелігійні мотиви в сучасному мистецтві)
1974	Christian Maggiori	2006	2010		Swiss Professor of University of Applied Sciences and Arts
1974	Jillian Lerner	2006	2006	w	Canadian historian in 19th-century media and culture
1974	Andrew Philips Adega	2006	2015		Nigerian Doctor of Religious Studies (African Traditional Religion)
1974	Ya'ara Gil-Glazer	2006	2010	w	Israeli lecturer and academic staff member, Faculty of Social Sciences & Humanities
1974	Rui Dias	2007	2018		Portuguese Composer, researcher and media artist
1974	Sandra Mardesic	2007	2011	w	Croatian Research assistant, Department of Italian Language and Culture
1974	Natasha Myers	2007	2007	w	Canadian associate professor of anthropology
1974	Alexandra Heller-Nicholas	2008	2011	w	New Zealand film critic (horror film, sexual violence, ethics and aesthetics)
1974	Raha Sabet	2008	No	w	Iranian PhD Scholar in Gender, Culture and development Studies, Women's Studies
1974	Ralf Gaus	2008			German Professor for Religious Education
1974	Amjad Alsyouf	2009	2014		Jordanian Assistant Professor of English and Comparative Literature
1974	Ljubica Anđelković Džambić	2009	2019	w	Croatian member of Academy of Dramatic Art
1974	Dean Hughes	2010	No		British Professor and Deputy Faculty Pro Vice Chancellor Arts Design and Social Sciences
1974	Rabia Atiyah Kreishan	2011	No	w	Jordanian the English Language Instructor of the Language Center
1974	Eze Ekenedirichukwu	2012			Nigerian Lecturer I Department of Religion and Cultural Studies
1974	Darren Moore	2013	2013		Australian-British Lecture in Music
1974	Francesca Romana Capone	2013	No	w	Italian PhD student in classical and modern cultures
1974	Diane Neubauer	2015	No	w	American doctoral studies in Foreign Language and ESL Education
1974	Siti Kurnia Widiastuti	2015			Indonesian Doctor of Inter-Religious Studies